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Trends in Hygiene Education in Bangladesh

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to summarize existing research and provide a comprehensive overview of hygiene education in Bangladesh. Relevant academic papers featuring the title "Bangladesh, Hygiene Education" were gathered over a five-year period spanning from 2021 to 2025 via Google Scholar. Out of the literature found, seven specific papers focused directly on hygiene education initiatives within the country. Four of these collected papers centered on school settings, analyzing foundational health education issues like menstrual care and handwashing practices. The findings indicate that while Bangladesh maintains a well-developed school health system, there is a notable absence of student-led activities in these environments. To address this gap, the study highlights the potential of implementing Japanese-style education models to successfully foster experiential learning and critical thinking among diverse students.

Keywords: Bangladesh, hygiene education, school health system, Japanese-style education

Trends in Hygiene Education in Bangladesh

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The purpose of this study is to summarize existing research and provide an overview of hygiene education in Bangladesh. Papers with the title “Bangladesh, Hygiene Education” were collected over a five-year period from 2021 to 2025. Seven papers focused on hygiene education. Four of these papers were about schools and covered basic health education such as hand washing and menstrual care. While Bangladesh’s school health system is well-developed, no student-led activities were observed. This study demonstrated the potential for Japanese-style education to foster experiential learning and critical thinking among students.

Keywords: Bangladesh, hygiene education, school health system, Japanese-style education

Bangladesh and Education

It gained independence from Pakistan in 1971 and has a population of approximately 170 million. Its population is still growing. It has eight administrative districts, each named after its central city. The language spoken is Bengali, and the main religions are Islam (89.7%), Hinduism (9.2%), Buddhism (0.7%), and Christianity (0.3%). The proportion of households in the middle-income bracket has been increasing in recent years, particularly those in the upper middle-income bracket (US \$10,000 to US \$ 34,999) (Ministry of Economy, Trade, and Industry, 2024). Despite economic growth, the latest data shows that 37% of the population still lives below the poverty line.

Bangladesh’s education system has undergone significant development in recent years, due to political intervention and private

partnerships (Roy, Huq, and Rob, 2020). As a result, completion rates for primary education rose from 66% to 83% in 2009–2013, 65% for secondary education, and 29% for upper secondary education in 2000–2023. At the primary and secondary education levels, socioeconomic disparities between the highest and lowest economic classes have narrowed significantly, and gender equality has been achieved (Roy, Huq, and Rob, 2020).

However, Bangladesh has many geographically isolated communities, and is faced with challenges including remoteness, language, and resources, as well as hunger, climatic conditions such as flooding, and human trafficking. In fact, Bangladesh’s learning poverty rate (the percentage of children who cannot read and understand basic texts by the age of 10) is expected to be 51% by 2024 (UNESCO, 2024).

Meanwhile, more than half of all secondary school students in the country use private tutors. This practice is so common that it is called as the “shadow education system.” Surveys show that payments to private tutors are the largest expenditure on education for Bangladeshis, accounting for 29% of all education-related costs by parents. The government allocates 2% of its gross domestic product (GDP) to education, the second lowest in South Asia and lower than many other countries at a similar stage of development (Roy, Huq, and Rob, 2020). Quality of teachers is an issue as well, and corporal punishment of students is not uncommon (UNICEF, 2020). This means that the SDGs’ goal of sustainable quality education is not being achieved. Furthermore, floods have led to widespread outbreaks of tropical infectious diseases such as dysentery (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2020). COVID-19 has also forced primary, secondary, and university schools to close for over a year.

Regarding inclusive education, Acharja et al. (2025) reports that poverty and low parental education levels are strongly associated with limited access to learning materials, nutrition, psychosocial support, and a voice at home and at school. They also report that children in rural areas, especially girls, face constraints such as limited mobility, early marriage, and reduced social participation. Meanwhile, children in urban areas enjoy greater opportunities and recognition. Despite robust legal frameworks (the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, and national policies reports), uneven teacher knowledge of inclusive education policies, limited training and resources, and differences in adult awareness hinder their implementation. Achieving inclusive education requires a long-term, integrated strategy that combines poverty reduction, rights-based education laws, teachers’ professional development,

gender-responsive policies, rural resource allocation, and mechanisms to promote children's participation. Alam et al. (2025) shows that school closures due to the COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated existing inequalities and hindered the learning, psychological, and social development of children with disabilities. Acharja et al. (2025) documents that persistent poverty, inadequate wages, malnutrition, and poor living conditions in tea plantation communities, a legacy of British colonial rule, perpetuate educational exclusion. Specifically, they demonstrate that parental illiteracy and long working hours reduce awareness and engagement in their children's education, significantly hindering students' motivation, support at home, and long-term academic progress. Acharja et al. (2025) demonstrate that poor enforcement of labor and education policies, combined with negative attitudes from teachers and peers, exacerbates discrimination and exclusion. They report that limited teacher training in inclusive education and systematic neglect by tea plantation authorities further hinder the realization of inclusive education. Eliminating educational disparities requires sustainable schooling through concrete government policies, public understanding, teacher training, and the voices of struggling students.

Health and hygiene

The average life expectancy is 74.67 years in 2021. Healthy life expectancy, or the period during which people can live without health problems limiting their daily activities, is 64.3 years for men and 64.4 years for women (World Bank, 2023). In 1990, average life expectancy was 58.21 years. This represents an increase of 20 years over approximately 30 years. The proportion of deaths and causes of death in 1990 and 2017 was compared. In 1990, tropical infectious diseases such as malaria, hepatitis A, dengue fever, and typhoid accounted for

more than 60% of deaths. However, a 2019 survey found that non-communicable diseases were the leading cause of death, accounting for 73.2% of deaths. Infectious diseases decreased to 20.3% (Ministry of Economy, Trade, and Industry, 2024). The breakdown of causes of death in 2017 showed that cardiovascular disease was the most common at 36.14%, followed by neoplasms at 11.2% and diabetes and kidney disease at 4.99%. As such, causes of death have changed in line with economic growth.

Public medical institutions are inexpensive but have long waiting times. In recent years, wealthier families or individuals prefer private medical institutions, or in some cases, overseas medical institutions for treatment. Most private medical institutions are located in Dhaka (Ministry of Economy, Trade, and Industry, 2024).

Health policy

There is no mandatory insurance system, but the Ministry of Health has been formulating a plan to enroll the poor in health insurance since 2012. There are private health insurance systems for the middle class and above.

Health policy, the goals set for 2011 include improving the nutritional status of the nation's citizens, ensuring easy access to health services for all citizens, reducing child and maternal mortality, enhancing family planning services, and minimizing overseas travel for treatment and improving services for the intellectually and physically disabled and elderly. The Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) also reports that projects are being implemented on themes such as infectious disease control and maternal and child health, including a project to improve the water and health environment in the Paigasa region by the Welfare University, and a maternal and child health and health system improvement project (Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry, 2024).

Bangladesh has made steady progress toward achieving its health goals (World Data Bank, HLSP 2010). In 2019, there were six doctors and four nurses per 10,000 people, lower than the regional average for the Asia-Pacific region (14 doctors and 30 nurses) (Fitch Solutions, 2019). Despite the shortage of doctors and hospitals, maternal, infant, and child mortality rates have declined significantly over the past decade. Furthermore, while disparities in the burden of disease between income groups remain significant, they are narrowing. Widespread access to informal healthcare providers and drug dealers has made drug treatment for common illnesses affordable for all but the poorest. However, many people purchase unnecessary medications, leading to excessive costs and the risk of side effects (Iqbal et al., 2013).

Purpose of this study

The purpose of this study is to summarize the previous research accumulated to date and provide an overview of hygiene education in Bangladesh. As a result, we believe that the challenges of hygiene education in Bangladesh will be clarified, and future directions will be indicated.

Method

Research method

Google Scholar was used to collect research papers with the title "Bangladesh, Hygiene Education" from a 10-year period ranging from 2014 to 2025. The research papers were divided into research subjects, content, and region, and then examined.

Result

1. Research on hygiene education in Bangladesh

In terms of overseas papers, a search on Google Scholar for papers with the title "Bangladesh, Hygiene Education" from 2021 to 2025 yielded seven papers. Table 1 shows the results categorized by research subject, content, and region.

Table 1: Research on hygiene education in Bangladesh

Research subjects	Content	District
1 Young children and families (Alam et al., 2025)	The study investigated the relationship between home hygiene and school enrollment rates. Children in homes with basic handwashing facilities were more likely to receive early childhood education and also had higher school enrollment rates.	Nationwide
2 Children and adults (Sato, 2017)	Visual training using two types of posters and flip cards was conducted for waste collectors. The developed materials, a six-day hygiene training program was conducted for 40 households that collect waste.	Khulna City
3 Low birth weight infants at term (Shafique, 2016)	Infection prevention practices (water-based hand sanitizer and minerals for one year) and improved nutrition (vitamin-fortified micronutrient powder).	Dhaka Division of Bangladesh and Gazipur District of South Asia
4 Junior and senior high school girls (Rahman et al., 2024)	Six months of menstrual hygiene education using a mobile app.	Rural School
5 Adolescent girl (Mohamed, 2024)	Menstrual hygiene education: Providing proper menstrual hygiene education to Rohingya adolescent girls.	Rohingya minors' assistance
6 Elementary school students (Biswas, 2017)	Hand washing and hygiene education to prevent influenza-like illnesses.	Dhaka city elementary school
7 Elementary school students (Grover, 2018)	Comparing the effects of a nudge intervention and high-intensity hygiene education aimed at improving handwashing behavior.	Rural

Hygiene education in the area

From the Bangladesh Demographic and Health Survey, Alam et al. (2025) found that children in households with basic handwashing facilities were more likely to receive early childhood education and have higher school enrollment rates. Sato (2018) developed visual hygiene education materials for waste collectors using two types of posters and flip cards. Using the developed materials, a six-day hygiene training program was conducted for 40 waste picker households. The training focused primarily on methods to support improvements in daily hygiene and health

processes in waste collection. Quantitative and qualitative feedback were collected from waste collectors, and the effectiveness of the training in developing hygiene education materials was reported. Shafique (2016) investigated the effectiveness of the targeted use of water-based hand sanitizer and mineral- and vitamin-fortified micronutrient powder in preventing infection and improving nutritional intake in full-term low-birthweight infants, thereby reducing growth retardation. The use of mineral- and vitamin-fortified micronutrient powder significantly reduced growth retardation in full-term low-birthweight infants.

Hygiene education in schools

Grover (2018) compared the effects of a nudge intervention and high-intensity hygiene education aimed at improving handwashing behavior in primary schools in Bangladesh. Nudge theory, based on behavioral economics, is a method for encouraging desirable choices without forcing people to act. Specifically, the nudges consisted of paved walkways, brightly painted walkways, and painted shoe prints connecting toilets and hand-washing areas. Regarding hygiene education, students learned about the importance of handwashing and how to wash their hands. The habit of washing hands with soap after using the toilet became established.

Rahman et al. (2024) conducted a six-month mobile phone-based menstrual health and hygiene program for 172 high school girls in Chandpur, Bangladesh, using community health care workers. Specifically, the program covered menstrual cycles, hygiene practices, health risks associated with unhygienic menstrual practices, use and disposal of menstrual products, and availability of menstrual products. The effectiveness of mobile health education was demonstrated. Mohamed (2024) implemented a menstrual hygiene management toolkit (MHM toolkit) as part of the school curriculum for Rohingya adolescent girls at a learning center in a refugee camp. Specifically, the school provided information on menstrual hygiene management, menstrual knowledge, private toilets, menstrual products, and menstrual information booklets. Rohingya adolescent girls received basic information about puberty and menstruation, eliminating misconceptions and taboos about menstruation. Biswas et al. (2017) distributed hand sanitizers to 12 primary schools in Dhaka city along with an educational intervention. Students were encouraged to use hand sanitizer at specific times at school

and were instructed to cover their mouths and noses with their upper arms when coughing or sneezing. No intervention was administered to 12 control schools. After adjusting gender, the incidence of laboratory-confirmed influenza was 55% lower in the intervention group compared to the control group (intervention group: 3%; control group: 6%, $p = 0.008$).

Utilizing school health education

Four of the seven studies focused on schools. Furthermore, they focused on basic health education, such as handwashing and menstrual hygiene. Furthermore, no efforts were found to promote hygiene education among students themselves. It is clear that hygiene education is a prominent issue in Bangladesh. This is a shared understanding not only among the government but also among the public. Most of Bangladesh's land area is comprised of a delta, where three major rivers—the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Meghna—flow. The natural threats associated with this delta are immeasurable. Specifically, annual rainy season floods are a boon for the land, but also a disaster that threatens people's lives. Furthermore, because the country is located at the northern end of the Bay of Bengal, it is prone to powerful cyclones and suffers frequent damage from storm surges. In this context, Bangladesh was once known as the "home of cholera," a region plagued by water-related infectious diseases. The school health education system has been established based on this backdrop.

The Department of Health Education, under the Directorate General of Health Services of the Government of Bangladesh, provides health education support to primary and secondary schools at the national, district, and sub-district levels. Health education officers at various administrative levels are responsible for organizing health education sessions in schools. They also

conduct training programs on school health education for schoolteachers and community leaders to develop healthy school environments and ensure the cooperation of school communities. Specifically, they provide materials such as posters, leaflets, booklets, modules, and banners on various health issues and programs to schools.

In addition, 64 model health education village elementary schools have been established, and each school in the model health education village has a "school health committee" consisting of schoolteachers, local health staff, parents, local leaders, and representatives of the committee chair and committee members. Health education officers play a catalytic role in developing collaboration between the health and education sectors.

School health clinics are staffed by two doctors and one pharmacist. Doctors visit schools to screen students and provide referrals to specialists. Special attention is also paid to vision screening, oral and dental health, and ENT care. There are 23 school health clinics across Bangladesh, supporting 1,573 schools. In 2014, 63,129 students received care. Additionally, health education officers from the Ministry of Health and Family Affairs provide training and support to teachers in providing first aid and health education (UNESCO, 2021). This support has enabled the school health education program to be implemented down to the village level (Department of Health and Education, 2023). In this environment, with primary school completion rates increasing in recent years, the enhancement of school health education is expected to have a significant impact on improving sanitation throughout Bangladesh.

Experiential learning for students through Japanese-style education

The country aims to cultivate a balanced mix of intellectual, moral, and physical abilities, and to develop industrial human

resources through primary and secondary education, high-quality science and mathematics education, ICT education, and vocational schools (EDU-Port Nippon, 2025). Therefore, learning incorporates not only knowledge but also student activities. According to the 2023 Global Competitiveness Index, Bangladesh's quality of higher education ranks 120, scoring only 24.91 out of 100, significantly below the global average of 47.8 (World Economic Forum, 2023). Developed countries emphasize experiential learning, critical thinking, and research-based education. In contrast, Bangladesh tends to have a strong tendency toward cramming lessons. Looking at the proportion of lessons devoted to concepts related to the development of reasoning skills, Bangladeshi teachers, while conducting observational activities, spent little time on questions that encourage students to make logical inferences using principles and laws of natural phenomena, such as "questions that prompt thought" and "integration with existing knowledge." Furthermore, while they conducted group and individual work, these primarily served to confirm that students were accurately answering questions based on what they had learned (Kono, 2018). Therefore, it may be necessary to incorporate the experiential learning based on student activities in Japanese education and develop it into inquiry-based learning. Ishikawa (2022) showed Indian students a video of a ventilation experiment created by high school students in a Japanese school health committee. He also conducted classroom activities that embrace diversity, which students praised as "enriching our individuality" and "helping us grow" (Ishikawa, 2024). Japanese education encompasses not only subjects but also student committee activities. The participation of students in school health committees can create a community that has been lacking until now, and it has the potential to foster experiential

learning and critical thinking among diverse students.

Hygiene education can be tailored to the actual situation and the use of the internet and artificial intelligence.

The percentage of households in Bangladesh that have access to basic sanitation (toilet) services (specifically, toilets that are not shared with neighboring households) is 59%. Additionally, the percentage of people who have basic hygiene facilities at home (specifically, the percentage of people who have access to handwashing facilities with water and soap) is 62% (UNICEF, 2024). Education that can improve hygiene in line with the actual situation in Bangladesh is important. Furthermore, the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (2023) reports that less than 20% of children in Bangladesh have access to digital learning.

Meanwhile, the Bangladeshi government has adopted the “Smart Bangladesh 2041” policy, which aims to cultivate smart citizens by 2041. Specifically, it aims to cultivate citizens who are not just able to use the internet, but who also have the ability to use digital technology (digital literacy) (Bangladesh Planning Commission, 2020). It aims for 100% digital literacy and 100% enrolment up to the secondary education (high school) level, particularly among young people. Therefore, it may be necessary to consider using the internet and artificial intelligence for health education as well.

Future challenges

Students who will go through Japanese-style education in Bangladeshi schools would go through the learning that fosters critical thinking. Education is a culture and cannot be imposed by other countries. The implementation of Japanese-style education requires careful consideration by Bangladeshi teachers and researchers. It will then be necessary to implement it and obtain

evaluations not only from students but also from teachers and parents and move forward and develop it.

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